

THERMAL HISTORY EFFECTS ON MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF VINYLESTER RESIN

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ABSTRACT

The thermal history during curing of a polyester resin depends upon the rate of heat loss from its surface and is consequently a function of the area/volume ratio. In order to examine the effect of these differences in the cure cycle, general purpose polyester and vinylester resins were prepared with varying thermal histories. The thermal histories were designed to approximate the natural cure cycle for varying geometry (specifically surface to volume ratio). The effect of maximum cure temperature on fracture properties was measured. Impact energy to break and fracture toughness, K_{Ic} , are greater in samples with lower maximum cure temperature. These results have implications for the construction of massive glass reinforced polyester components for use in high stress and corrosive environments.

Keywords: polyester resin, cure reaction, exotherm, toughness, strain corrosion cracking resistance

1. INTRODUCTION

The expanding use of glass fibre reinforced polyester (GRP) resin in structural applications in corrosive environments necessitates an understanding of processing effects on properties and long term behaviour. Potential off shore applications for GRP are presently hampered by the high safety factors for GRP materials owing to the uncertainties associated with processing/property effects and long term durability. One of the reasons for the variability in mechanical properties of GRP stems from the difficulty of controlling the resin temperatures attained during the manufacturing process. This problem is particularly marked in the manufacture of massive components, where the thermal history is controlled not only by the reaction kinetics but also by the thermal conductivity of the resin and the rate of heat loss from the surface of the specimen to the environment. These temperature variations give rise to changes in the mechanical properties of the resin matrix and hence to the stress corrosion cracking resistance of GRP which hinders the use of GRP resins.

The work of Hull and coworkers^{1,2} has shown that the strain corrosion cracking characteristics of GRP are influenced by the fracture toughness of the resin. Fracture toughness depends upon degree of cure which is a function of thermal history of the cured polyester. There is little systematic understanding of the quantitative relationship between cure conditions and mechanical properties of cured polyester. There is less information available concerning the effect of the dimensions of the material (and hence the heat losses from the materials) on the temperatures attained during the cure reaction. This paper presents the first stage of a study of the effect of thermal history on fracture properties of general purpose polyester and polyvinylester resins. The aim of the research is to establish criteria for production control of GRP which reduce the susceptibility of the product to stress corrosion cracking.

2. EXPERIMENTAL

2.1 Materials and test methods

The general purpose polyester was supplied by Ferro Corp. The epoxy vinyl ester was supplied by Dow Chemical (Australia). The catalyst (methyl ethyl ketone peroxide, MEKP 40%), promoter (cobalt naphthenate 6%) and accelerator (N,N dimethylaniline, DMA 10%) were obtained from Fibreglass International. The concentrations of the catalyst, promoter, and accelerator used were 1%, 0.2% and 0.5%, respectively.

The promoter and accelerator were mixed into a small batch of resin (2 litres) which was used within the next two weeks. The catalyst was added just prior to curing and mixed until a uniform straw colour was obtained. The catalysed resin was then poured into a teflon mould. Two different mould shapes were used for the mechanical tests; (i) discs of 60mm diameter, thickness varying up to 5mm, (ii) tiny square prisms with dimensions 16 x 16 x 11mm. The discs were used for instrumented impact tests and bars cut from the discs were used for three point bend tests. The square prism samples were prepared for fracture toughness test using small compact tension samples of dimensions 15.8 x 15.2 x 9 mm.

2.1 Temperature profile

The samples sizes chosen were sufficiently small to ensure uniformity of temperature throughout the sample. (The temperature distribution during cure was measured by placing multiple thermocouples in a single sample). Subsequently, the temperatures attained during the curing reaction were measured by the aid of a single thermocouple immersed in one sample of identical shape to the experimental test pieces. The temperature profile during cure reaction as a function of surface to volume ratio was determined in order to obtain data on temperature rise for various sample geometries.

2.2 Calorimetric measurements

The differential scanning calorimetric (DSC) measurements were conducted in a Perkin-Elmer DSC-7. Exothermic heats of reactions were measured using a scanning rate of 10°C/min from 25°C to 150°C. The scanning rate was chosen to approximate the rate of temperature rise measured previously in curing samples. A resin sample was catalysed by mixing it with MEKP for 30 seconds. The liquid samples were sealed into volatile liquid pans. The weight of the pan with the sample was measured before and after the run to check whether there was any loss of sample during the measurement.

The degree of cure of samples cured with differing maximum temperature was measured in aluminium pans at the same scanning rate and over the same range of temperatures. The degree of cure of samples that were machined to size for the mechanical tests was measured and compared with samples having the same temperature profile but no machining. This measurement was done in order to examine the extent to which any heat generation during machining might have affected the degree of cure. No such additional curing was detected, thus machined samples could be confidently used to assess the effect of temperature profile on mechanical properties.

2.3 Mechanical tests

The effect of temperature profile on mechanical properties was determined on samples of the same dimensions. The various temperature profiles within the sample were produced by a temperature controlled oven programmed to mimic the temperatures obtained in different sample sizes as measured previously by a thermocouple reading. Sample temperature was monitored in the oven. Post curing of the samples was not carried out in order to imitate the manufacturing procedure for massive components. The tests were performed 16 days after cure.

There are several test methods described in the literature to determine fracture toughness of polymers. Compact tension specimens (CTS)³, double cantilever beam⁴ and three point bend⁵ tests require relatively large amounts of material per specimen. Our main concern in choosing a test

sample configuration was to minimize the temperature distribution within the sample and to minimize the temperature attained during cure due to sample size. It was necessary to use small samples that when cured at room temperature would not reach higher than than 30-40°C. Different temperature profiles could then be produced for this geometry by exposing the samples to elevated temperatures during cure in an oven.

2.3.1 Impact tests

The instrumented impact test was chosen in the initial stage of the work as a technique to determine the most severe loading of a sample and to measure the failure energy⁶. The impact test is considered a useful technique for determining the fracture toughness of glassy polymers because it simulates the high loading and high strain rates which materials encounter in many applications³. Impact tests can be used as well to determine the brittle/ductile transition point of a material under impulsive loading⁷. Brittle behaviour of polyester materials can cause catastrophic failure of structures. Determination of the onset of brittle failure at a fixed strain rate as a function of the thermal profile during cure can be used to improve structural performance.

Figure 1 shows a typical result for a ductile specimen. The baseline is identified as the initial "no load" part of the trace, and the computer adjusts all the data using this zero value. The effective "no load" level is a compound of the offset levels arising from the transducer, power supply, amplifier and transient recorder. The initial rising part of the load (the gradient) gives an estimate of rigidity of the specimen and the intercept is used as a zero for the subsequent evaluation of displacement. The yield and break points are identified, both as load levels and displacement values, and the respective areas under the curve defined by the baseline, gradient and load trace to yield and to break are evaluated. These areas represent the impact energies required to cause yield and fracture of the specimen. Occasional ringing in the transducer obscures the results, and these traces must be discarded.

Figure 1. Force-displacement results for ductile failure under impact.

2.3.2 Fracture toughness

The ASTM standard for measuring fracture toughness of metals⁸ was used for polymers as described by Williams⁹. Small polymer CTS (width=1.27cm) have been shown previously to yield consistent, reproducible results¹⁰. The compact tension specimen is shown in Figure 2. The thickness, B , was chosen to satisfy the requirement in ASTM standard E-399 that the minimum thickness $B \leq 2.5(K_{Ic}/\sigma_{ys})^2$, where K_{Ic} is the measured critical stress intensity factor, and σ_{ys} is the yield strength of the polyester. The size limit on the width, W , was taken from previous work¹⁰ which showed that the crack length a must be large compared to the dimensions of the crack tip plastic zone. In addition ASTM D-399 requires $a \geq 2.5(K_{Ic}/\sigma_{ys})^2$. For the samples tested in this work $B = 9\text{mm}$, $W = 12.7$ and all other dimensions were according to the requirements in ASTM D-399. Individual samples were cured and machined to size. A sharp starting notch was made by a saw and a natural crack was introduced by tapping a new razor blade placed in the notch. Fracture of the specimens was performed on an Instron Model 4505 at a crosshead speed of 1mm/min. Critical stress intensity factors were calculated by using the expression:

$$K_Q = \left(P_Q / BW^{\frac{3}{2}} \right) \cdot f(a/W) \quad (1)$$

where:

P_Q = maximum load, after validity criterion was established (kN)

B = specimen thickness (cm)

W = specimen width (cm)

a = crack length (cm)

f = geometrical factor

The geometrical factor is expressed as:

$$f(x) = \frac{(2+x)(0.886 + 4.64x - 13.32x^2 + 14.72x^3 - 5.6x^4)}{(1-x)^{\frac{3}{2}}} \quad (2)$$

where $x = a/W$.

The validity of this equation⁴ is limited to the range $0.3 \leq a/W \leq 0.7$.

Figure 2. Compact tension specimen geometry.

2.3.3 Three point bend

The elastic modulus was measured using ASTM standard D-790¹¹. Bars were machined to size: width = 25mm, depth = 2mm, and length = 50mm.

The critical strain energy release rate was calculated using the expression:-

$$G_{Ic} = \frac{(1-\nu^2)K_{Ic}^2}{E} \quad (3)$$

where ν = Poisson's ratio and
 E = elastic modulus.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Temperatures profiles

The effect of surface to volume ratio on temperatures attained during cure at room temperature (20°C) was determined using the general purpose (GP) polyester and the vinylester. Figure 3 shows the temperature profile during the cure of discs of GP polyester with identical surface area (diameter 100mm) but with varying thicknesses. The insulation effects of the teflon mould ensure that the surface area is effectively constant. The peak temperature attained and the time required to reach it

vary between 143°C and 26min for the 5mm thick sample to 50°C and 42min for the 2mm thick sample.

Figure 3. Temperature profile during cure of GP polyester as a function of time for various sample thicknesses.

Temperature profiles for the vinyl ester are represented in Figure 4. The peak temperature obtained and the time required to reach it vary between 120°C and 26min for a sample 10mm thick to 30°C and 55min for a sample 2mm thick. The vinyl ester resin is less exothermic than the GP resin; however, the trend of increasing maximum cure temperature with decreasing surface to volume ratio is similar in both polyesters.

Figure 4. Temperature profile during cure of epoxy vinyl ester as a function of time for various sample thicknesses.

3.2 Calorimetric measurements

The total measured heat of curing reaction of the vinyl ester is 0,34kJ/g as shown in Figure 5. At the end of this run the sample was cooled rapidly and re-scanned under the same conditions; no evidence of residual heat of reaction indicated that the polyester was fully cured.

The residual heat of reaction of samples with different temperature profiles was measured by DSC as a function of time after cure. Figure 6 summarizes the exothermal data. The degree of cure was calculated by dividing the residual heat of reaction by the total heat of curing. The degree of cure reaches the equilibrium value of 85% cure in all samples that were under-cured. Testing samples 16 days after cure ensures that all samples have reached the equilibrium degree of cure. The heats of reaction for fully cured samples are consistent with values published in the literature¹².

Figure 5. DSC thermogram for epoxy vinyl ester curing reaction.

Figure 6. The degree of cure of epoxy vinyl ester for different peak cure temperatures as a function of time.

The degree of cure of samples that were machined for mechanical tests was determined and compared with samples that were not machined. The residual heat of reaction was unchanged by machining.

3.3 Mechanical tests

The instrumented impact results and CTS results are presented in Table 1. The results in Table 1 illustrate a decrease in fracture energy and fracture toughness with increased maximum cure temperature. Population standard deviations on 10 samples per data set indicate a 50% scatter for the impact tests compared to a 10% scatter for the fracture toughness tests. The impact tests probe fracture initiation as the crack starts at an intrinsic flaw. The fracture toughness measurements by CTS probe fracture propagation by introducing a flaw. If the flaw in the CTS is reproducible then it seems reasonable that the standard deviation for crack propagation would be lower than for crack initiation.

The modulus of elasticity results of the three point bend tests are also presented in Table 1. The critical strain energy release rate G_{IC} is calculated using Equation 3. Poisson's ratio has not been measured in these samples, but it is assumed to be 0.3. It is possible that the value of Poisson's ratio differs between the 35°C maximum temperature samples and the 100°C maximum temperature samples. The extreme case would be $\nu = 0.5$ for the 35°C T_{max} samples and $\nu = 0.3$ for the 100°C T_{max} samples which still results in a significant difference in G_{IC} for the two data sets.

Table 1. Mechanical property data of polyvinylester resin.

Maximum Cure Temperature (°C)	Impact Energy (mJ)	Fracture Toughness K_{Ic} ($\mu\text{Pa m}^{1/2}$)	Modulus of Elasticity E (GPa)	Critical Strain Energy Release Rate G_{Ic} (kJ/m ²)
35	260 ± 110	0.549 ± 0.051	2.87 ± 0.15	0.096 ± 0.005
100	143 ± 78	0.498 ± 0.035	3.46 ± 0.08	0.064 ± 0.003

4. CONCLUSIONS

Surface to volume ratio has been shown to have a marked effect on the temperature profiles during cure of polyesters. Temperatures over 120°C are reached in geometries common to commercial lay-up practice. The mechanical property results indicate that the maximum temperature attained during cure is important to toughness. For structural applications the mechanical property data alone dictate a maximum temperature criterion during production. The toughness data have further ramifications for load bearing parts in corrosive environments such as massive parts for off shore applications. Preliminary work in our research group as well as that of other workers^{1,2} have established a relationship between fracture toughness and strain corrosion cracking (SCC) resistance in polyester resins. It is a goal of our work to measure SCC resistance for samples of differing thermal history and to relate SCC behaviour to production variables. From the results of this work it is hoped not only to develop criteria for the allowable exotherms during manufacture but also to establish design techniques which enable the attainment of the criteria.

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